

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Characterizing e-Liquids

This application highlight addresses the measurement of e-liquids for use in e-cigarettes using the Transient Hot Wire (THW).

In the design and performance of e-cigarettes (vapes), the thermal behaviour of the e-liquid plays a critical role in determining vaporization efficiency, aerosol composition, and overall user experience. In these devices, a battery-powered coil (heating element) raises the temperature of the surrounding e-liquid, turning it into an inhalable vapour. The efficiency of this process depends on heat transfer characteristics, as conduction through the e-liquid is the primary transfer mechanism. The coil's heat must conduct into the liquid, often via a wick that holds the liquid, since there is minimal fluid motion (convection) in the confined space of a vape coil assembly. Thermal conductivity (k) is the property that quantifies how well a material conducts heat. For e-liquids, this determines how quickly and uniformly the coil's heat distributes into the fluid. If an e-liquid cannot conduct heat away efficiently, even a modest-sized coil can develop a steep temperature gradient: extremely hot at the coil surface and much cooler just a short distance away.

Figure 1 – e-Cigarette vapour production, which is impacted by the thermal conductivity of the e-liquid.

e-liquids are typically comprised of propylene glycol (PG) and vegetable glycerin (VG), each with distinct thermal and physical properties that influence how heat is absorbed and transferred during operation. VG exhibits a higher thermal conductivity than PG, approximately 0.285 W/mK^1 , compared to PG's 0.206 W/mK^2 , suggesting it can conduct heat more effectively. However, VG's higher boiling point and viscosity mean it requires significantly more energy to vaporize, often resulting in slower heat transfer within the wick and less efficient vapour production. PG, despite its lower thermal conductivity,

¹ https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/thermal-conductivity-liquids-d_1260.html

² <https://s3.us-east-2.amazonaws.com/keller-heartt-assets/Data+Sheets/Specs-TG-Propylene-Glycol-HTF.pdf>

vaporizes more readily due to its lower boiling point and volatility, making it a key component in achieving rapid and consistent vaporization.

Recent research published in *Nature Scientific Reports* highlights the critical role of thermal conductivity in the heat and mass transfer dynamics of e-cigarette systems.³ The study found that PG-rich liquids tend to exhibit higher thermal efficiency, meaning a greater proportion of input energy is converted into vapour rather than residual heat. This efficiency stems not solely from thermal conductivity, but from the interplay between heat absorption, vaporization kinetics, and fluid transport within the wick. As vaping progresses, PG is preferentially vaporized, enriching the remaining liquid in VG and increasing the likelihood of overheating and forming harmful degradation products such as acrolein. These findings underscore that while VG may conduct heat better on paper, its physical characteristics can hinder efficient vaporization. Thus, understanding and managing the thermal properties of these liquids is essential for optimizing device performance and ensuring chemical safety.

Figure 2 - C-Therm Trident instrument configured with Transient Hot Wire, providing the optimal means of testing e-liquids.

C-Therm's Trident platform offers a versatile solution equipped with multiple sensor options tailored for different sample types. This enables the precise characterization of the thermal behaviour of various materials and sample formats. For testing liquids, the Transient Hot Wire (THW) is an excellent choice due to its short test times and low power inputs, which are two factors that help mitigate the impact of convection during measurement. The following data demonstrates the use of the THW in testing the different components of e-liquids and a commercially available e-liquid containing 70% VG and 30% PG.

³ Gao, Y., et al. (2021). *A numerical study on capillary-evaporation behavior of porous wick in electronic cigarettes*. *Nature Scientific Reports*. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-89685-4>

Figure 3 - Thermal conductivity results on materials related to e-liquids using THW.

The results above are the average of 5 consecutive measurements. Both PG and VG align with the expected literature values (within 3%). Comparing a 70/30 mix to a commercially available e-liquid, we observe near identical results (0.268 vs 0.263 W/mK).

Beyond e-liquids, Trident's thermal conductivity capabilities are driving innovation across multiple components of e-cigarettes, enabling engineers to better control heat flow, safety, and user comfort. Testing porous ceramic cores and wicks supports more uniform heating and reduced "dry hits". Characterizing mouthpiece and vapour-path materials guides the choice of polymers, glasses, or ceramics that stay comfortable at the lips while managing condensation. Testing tank, cartridge bodies, seals, and center posts informs how heat spreads through the liquid reservoir and structural parts. Evaluating housings, battery sleeves, potting compounds, PCBs, and thermal interface materials enables safer, cooler-touch devices with improved electronic reliability. Together, these measurements allow design teams to select and tune materials at every stage of the device architecture, utilizing Trident data to translate thermal management targets into specific material and design decisions.

About Us:

C-Therm is the world leader in thermal conductivity instrumentation for test and measurement of polymers, ceramics, composites, insulation, textiles, and a wide range of other materials. Headquartered in Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada, C-Therm specializes in non-destructive thermal analysis solutions that empower researchers, manufacturers, and quality control professionals across various industries – from aerospace and automotive to electronics and energy storage.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit
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